

Determination of Silver (I) and Gold (III) from the Rate of Catalysed Substitution of α - α' -Dipyridyl for Cyanide in Potassium Ferrocyanide

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Silver (I) and Gold (III) catalyse the decomposition of ferrocyanide in the presence of α - α' -dipyridyl, the liberated iron (II) forms red coloured $[\text{Fe}(\text{dipy})_3]^{2+}$. The rate of formation of this complex has been followed by measuring the absorbance at 520 nm. In the presence of excess of ferrocyanide and α - α' -dipyridyl, the initial rate of formation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{dipy})_3]^{2+}$ is dependent on the concentration of catalyst, viz., Ag^+ or Au^{3+} . The reactions have been carried out at a strictly controlled pH of value between 5.0 and 7.5 and at a constant temperature around 25–30°. Thus, trace amounts of silver (1.67×10^{-5} to $3 \times 10^{-4} M$) and gold (1.65×10^{-5} to $1.5 \times 10^{-4} M$) have been determined. The effects of various diverse ions on the determination have been studied.

THE rate of a chemical reaction is often used as an analytical tool as it is dependent on the concentration of the reactants or in some case on the concentration of a catalyst. The measurement of the 'initial rate' has found wide application for reactions catalysed by enzymes. But when the reaction to be followed is purely inorganic or involves complexes with organic reagents these have been allowed to proceed for some time and then quenched after a 'fixed time' interval. Thus, silver (I) and gold (III) have been determined from the rate of several reactions catalysed by these ions using the fixed time method¹⁻⁷.

The objective of the work reported is to determine trace quantities of silver (I) and gold (III) from their catalytic actions using the replacement of cyanide in ferrocyanide by α - α' -dipyridyl as the indicator reaction from the measurement of the 'initial rate'. The effects of various factors influencing the reaction have also been studied to ensure the reproducibility of the results. The same indicator reaction, where the formation of iron (II)- α - α' -dipyridyl with λ_{max} at 520 nm is followed spectrophotometrically has been used before for the determination of mercury (II)⁸.

Experimental

Silver (I) Solution : A stock solution of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ silver nitrate (A.R., B.D.H.) was prepared. The metal content was determined by electro-deposition of silver.

Gold (III) Solution : A sample of gold chloride (75%) mixed with sodium chloride (J. Mathey) was dissolved in water; the gold content of the solution was estimated⁹ and this was suitably diluted to obtain a $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution.

Ferrocyanide Solution : As potassium ferrocyanide (G.R., S. Merck) is slightly sensitive to light, a fresh 0.1M solution was prepared each day.

α - α' -Dipyridyl Solution : An ethanolic solution of α - α' -dipyridyl (A.R., B.D.H.) of 0.1M strength was used.

Buffer solutions : Sodium acetate and acetic acid or bis (hydroxymethyl)-methylamine (B.D.H.) and sulphuric acid buffers of pH-values in the range of 4.5 to 8.5 were prepared.

Diverse ions : For studying the effect of diverse ions, in case of silver, only water soluble sulphates or nitrates were used. Several chlorides were also used in case of gold. When the effect of anions was studied either sodium or potassium salt was taken.

Apparatus : Absorbance measurements were carried out in a Hilger and Watts H 700 Uvispek Spectrophotometer with thermostatic attachment using 1 cm glass cuvettes. A Beckman UB spectrophotometer with intensity-time recorder was used in the preliminary experiments. A battery-operated bench-model Cambridge pH meter recording with an accuracy of ± 0.02 unit was used to measure the pH.

Procedure : All the solutions were kept for 1 hr in a thermostat maintained at the same temperature as the thermostatic cell-chamber of the spectrophotometer. Measured quantities of 0.1 M potassium ferrocyanide (0.3 ml) and 0.1 M α - α' -dipyridyl (0.3 ml) solutions were taken in each of two 1 cm glass cuvettes. Suitable volumes of a buffer solution were added to the cuvettes so that after adding a known amount of the catalyst solution (0.1 to 0.9 ml) in one of the cuvettes the total volume of the liquid in each one was exactly 3 ml. Normally a buffer of pH value ranging between 5.0 and 7.5, measured with an accuracy of ± 0.02 unit was used. Time was recorded from the addition of the catalyst and the optical absorbance at 520 nm was measured at intervals of 30 to 40 sec. for about 5 min.

Results

Calibration Curves : Curves obtained by plotting absorbance (A) values against time (t) show a

rapid increase in (A) initially and then a reduction in the rate. The rate of the reaction at the initial stage was found to be dependent on the concentration of the catalyst (Ag^+ or Au^{3+}).

When the initial rate of change in absorbance with time ($\Delta A/\Delta t$) was plotted against the concentration of Ag^+ or Au^{3+} , the calibration curves were obtained. Calibration curves for each of these catalysed reactions obtained under well defined conditions have been shown in Fig. 1. Similar curves could be drawn and used for other pH values and temperatures.

Effect of the concentration of ferrocyanide and α - α' -dipyridyl: A final concentration of $10^{-2}M$ dipyridyl was used as the rate was independent when the concentration of it was above $7 \times 10^{-3}M$ for Ag^+ and above $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ for Au^{3+} . The rate was found to be independent of the concentration of ferrocyanide when an excess of it ($0.1M$), with respect to the catalyst, was used.

Effect of pH: The initial rate of the reaction is very much sensitive to change in pH below 7.0, above which that the error introduced due to variation of pH will be minimised. The slowing down of the rate with the increase in pH may be due to the increased stability of the cyano-complexes of the catalysts or due to the decreased concentration of these in the solution on account of hydrolytic precipitation. A slight haziness was actually observed on addition of silver to the reaction mixture buffered at pH 8.0. Use of higher pH was more difficult in the presence of diverse ions due to hydrolytic precipitations and scarcity of suitable non-interfering buffers. Thus pH values between 5.0 and 7.5 were chosen, but rigid control was necessary. However, Fig. 1 indicates that good calibration curves could be obtained at different pH values.

Effect of temperature: The rate increases more rapidly for the reaction catalysed by Au^{3+} than Ag^+ . The thermostats were set around 25 to 30° with maximum variation of $\pm 1^\circ$ as this range was close to the room temperature.

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of various cations and anions on the determination of silver and gold have been studied. The tolerance limits have been listed in Table 1. In case of Ag^+ , chloride, bromide and iodide can also be tolerated until their concentrations exceed the solubility product of the corresponding silver halide. If excess of cyanide is added initially, permitting the formation of $[\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2]^-$, the rate becomes extremely slow rendering the determination impracticable. This effect is less pronounced in case of Au^{3+} due to the instability of the cyano-complex of Au^{3+} . The slowing down of the reaction with time may also be explained with the help of the stability constants of the cyano-complexes. With the accumulation of cyanide released from ferrocyanide the cyano-complexes are formed and the concentration of the catalyst ions is reduced, the extent being determined by the stability constant of the cyano-complex. This effect is more pronounced in the case of silver (I) and mercury (II)⁸ than gold (III) as $[\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ and $[\text{Hg}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ are quite stable¹⁰ with stability constants, 6.3×10^{20} and 10^{42} respectively.

Fig 1. Calibration curves. [A] Au^{3+} , pH 5.24, temp. 25° [B] Au^{3+} , pH 7.15, temp. 24° [C] Ag^+ , pH 5.41, temp. 30° [D] Ag^+ , pH 7.15, temp. 29°

TABLE I—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Determination of Ag^+ (Ag^+ taken, $1 \times 10^{-4}M$)		Determination of Au^{3+} (Au^{3+} taken, $1.13 \times 10^{-4}M$)	
Diverse ion	Tolerance limit ($10^{-4}M$)	Diverse ion	Tolerance limit ($10^{-4}M$)
Cu^{2+}	0.17	Cu^{2+}	0.17
Pb^{2+}	0.13	Pb^{2+}	1.33
Cd^{2+}	3.33	Tl^{2+}	0.67
Sn^{2+}	6.67	Sn^{2+}	0.16
Bi^{3+}	1.33	Bi^{3+}	0.67
AsO_3^{3-}	0.33	AsO_4^{3-}	0.33
SO_4^{2-}	13.33	Cl^-	13.33
PO_4^{3-}	13.33	Br^-	6.67
		I^-	6.67
		SO_4^{2-}	6.67
		CN^-	13.33
		$\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$	13.33

Thiosulphate completely masks the activity of Ag^+ , though moderate amounts of phosphate do not interfere. Thus gold could be determined in the presence of silver masked with thiosulphate. Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} in concentrations limited by the respective solubility product of their hydroxides do not interfere. The presence of Hg^{2+} has to be avoided as this ion catalyses the indicator reaction used.

Discussion

From the results presented above it is observed that trace amounts of Ag^+ (1.67×10^{-6} to $3 \times 10^{-4}M$) and Au^{3+} (1.65×10^{-5} to $1.5 \times 10^{-4}M$) can be determined from the catalytic action of these ions on the initial rate of the replacement of cyanide in ferrocyanide by α - α' -dipyridyl with relative deviations of $\pm 3.8\%$ and $\pm 4.2\%$ respectively. The catalytic effect of Au^{3+} is more pronounced than that of Ag^+ . The accuracy of this procedure is better than the same using 'fixed-time' method reported by earlier workers where rapid quenching of the reaction mixture from $\sim 65^\circ$ to below 20° was necessary. The efficiency in measuring the absorbance

3-4 times at 30-40 sec. intervals ensures better accuracy using the initial rate. The preliminary investigations carried out using an intensity-time recorder gave higher accuracy than claimed by the authors. However, the sensitivity of the reactions using fixed time method was higher. The total time required for measurements using the procedure described here does not exceed 3-4 minutes which reduces the chances of photochemical decomposition of ferrocyanide. However, this decomposition is a slow process and appropriate blanks were used.

The reaction mechanism suggested by Feigl and Caldas¹¹ has been accepted, as the information was sufficient for utilising the reaction for the determination of trace quantities of Ag⁺ or Au³⁺. The rate of the reaction has been found to be independent of the concentration of ferrocyanide, which is taken in excess. Yatsimirskii and Orlova¹² have reported similar observations for another comparable reaction between ferrocyanide and nitrobenzene with Au³⁺ as catalyst. The reaction is of the first order with respect to the concentration of Au³⁺ when ferrocyanide is in excess. The mechanism proposed for this reaction assumes the formation of an intermediate, [Fe(CN)₅·H₂O]³⁻ as the rate determining step.

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